

It's What You Span, Not How Many: The Distinct Value of Boundary-Spanner in Knowledge Production

Abstract

Current university policies regulate multi-sector careers through blunt quantitative caps, restricting external engagement without assessing its cross-sector value. This regulatory approach persists largely because the distinctive scientific value of individual "boundary-spanners" remains empirically undemonstrated at scale. Addressing this dual policy and empirical blind spot, we analyze 14.6 million publications to compare single-sector, team-based cross-sector, and boundary-spanner-led research. We provide evidence that boundary-spanner-led papers achieve significantly higher impact than single-sector papers (+8% in matched samples; OR = 1.20 for top-10% papers). Also, boundary-spanners achieve equivalent rates of top-tier research as cross-sector teams. Most importantly, we identify a phenomenon: sectoral breadth (diversity of sector types) yields substantially larger positive citation returns than institutional dispersion (total affiliations). Moreover, only institutional dispersion exhibits an inverted-U relationship, with marginal returns turning negative beyond 7-8 concurrent positions. These findings challenge the utility of blanket affiliation restrictions, calling for a transition from blind quantitative caps to qualitative frameworks prioritizing engagement diversity.

Keywords: boundary-spanner, academic labor market, cross-sector engagement, knowledge production

1. Introduction

1.1 Governing Multi-Sector Academic Careers: A Global Policy Challenge

Across modern academia, an increasing number of scientists maintain simultaneous affiliations that span different institutional sectors. A life scientist affiliates with a biomedical firm alongside her/his university position, a professor in drama serves concurrently as a theatre director, an agricultural scientist divides time between a university department and a government advisory role (Hanns J. Neubert, 2006; Lam, A., 2018; Stuart & Ding, 2006). These multi-sector configurations are a growing feature of academic labor markets worldwide, reflecting what Gibbons et al. (1994) described as "Mode 2" knowledge production that transcends traditional institutional boundaries.

Governments and universities have, in principle, actively encouraged cross-sector engagement. National innovation strategies routinely call for deeper university-industry-government collaboration (Etzkowitz & Leydesdorff, 2000), and funding agencies increasingly incentivize partnerships that bridge academic and

non-academic sectors (Perkmann et al., 2021). In practice, however, the regulatory frameworks governing individual researchers tell a different story. Across the globe, institutions have adopted policies that implicitly restrict the very cross-sector activity they ostensibly promote, doing so in a remarkably uniform way: by capping the time allocated to external engagement. In the United States, MIT¹ permits faculty to devote no more than 10%-20% of their time to outside activities. In the United Kingdom, Oxford² operates a "30-day rule" capping external commitments, while UCL³ limits academic consultancy to 40 days per year. In China, Peking University⁴ limits researchers to a maximum of three paid concurrent positions and 60 days of external work per year, while other institutions impose similar temporal boundaries ranging from 120 hours to three months annually (see full details in Appendix A).

These regulatory frameworks share three structural flaws. First, they are non-evidence-based: the thresholds—10% or 20% of time, 30 days per year, three positions—appear to reflect administrative convenience rather than empirical findings regarding optimal engagement. Second, they are undifferentiated: they treat intra-academic appointments (e.g., concurrent university positions) and cross-sector engagements as administratively identical, ignoring that the latter is intrinsically tied to the translation of knowledge from production to application. Third, they impose a one-size-fits-all uniformity across disciplines, overlooking that the external interactions required in clinical medicine differ structurally from those in pure mathematics. Ultimately, these policies rest on an unexamined assumption: that external engagements inherently distract from core academic duties. This framing obscures a critical consequence: by capping time undifferentiatedly, institutions may be actively suppressing a highly productive form of scholarly activity.

This assumption persists largely because the existing empirical literature has failed to distinguish between team-level and individual-level cross-sector integration. While extensive research has examined university-industry partnerships within the "Triple Helix" framework (Etzkowitz & Leydesdorff, 2000), it has overwhelmingly focused on the team level, evaluating for instance whether a paper involves co-authors from different sectors. Far less attention has been paid to individual-level boundary-spanning: the phenomenon of a single researcher simultaneously embedded in multiple sectors. If boundary-spanning individuals and cross-sector teams operate through fundamentally different knowledge integration mechanisms—internal cognitive synthesis vs. external team assembly—then findings derived from team-level research cannot simply be extrapolated to understand, let alone regulate, individual-level cross-sector engagement.

1.2 From Team Collaboration to Individual Human Capital: An Unaddressed Distinction

The relationship between researchers' cross-sector career arrangements and the knowledge they produce has been mainly studied at two levels of analysis. At the team level, prior studies on cross-sector collaboration, particularly university-industry partnerships, have examined what drives the assembly of researchers from different sectors into joint projects and how this affects outcomes (Perkmann et al., 2013, 2021; Tartari & Breschi, 2012). At the individual level, studies of scientist mobility have shown that researchers who move between sectors carry tacit knowledge (Crespi et al., 2007; Zucker & Darby,

1996) through enduring social ties (Agrawal et al., 2006; Breschi & Lissoni, 2009), serving as bridges for cross-sector knowledge flows.

However, mobility is only one form of individual-level cross-sector engagement. A researcher who moves from academia to industry experiences sectors sequentially, sequentially, gaining new knowledge while gradually losing currency in the former domain. But a growing number of researchers do not move between sectors; they simultaneously inhabit multiple sectors, maintaining concurrent affiliations that allow them to internalize diverse knowledge systems, institutional logics, and professional networks at the same time. This form of simultaneous multi-sector embedding differs from mobility in a fundamental way: instead of transferring knowledge across sectors as a depreciating stock, the embedded researcher continuously refreshes and synthesizes knowledge from all sectors in which they remain active, and can serve as a bridge facilitating effective exchange between otherwise disconnected domains.

Despite this conceptual distinction, the individual-level literature has traditionally prioritized sequential mobility, leaving the phenomenon of simultaneous embedding systematically underexplored. This matters because human capital configuration, rather than its mere quantity, has profound consequences for knowledge production (Stephan, 2012). An individual who internally synthesizes multiple knowledge systems represents a fundamentally different human capital configuration than either a mobile researcher with historical ties, or a multi-sector team. Yet existing evidence on the value of this individual-level multi-sector embedding remains, by researchers' own assessment, largely "anecdotal" (Bednarek et al., 2018; Posner & Cvitanovic, 2019), typically confined to qualitative case studies or small-sample interviews within specific domains. This gap leaves policymakers without a scientific basis for designing regulations around multi-sector academic careers.

1.3 Research Questions and Contributions

This study addresses this gap at the intersection of academic labor market research and the science of science, with three contributions.

First, we provide the first large-scale empirical test of whether individual multi-sector embedding, as distinct from team-based cross-sector collaboration, has a unique association with research impact. By classifying over 14.6 million publications into single-sector papers, team-based cross-sector papers, and boundary-spanner-led papers, we directly test the distinct value proposition of individual boundary-spanners: does it matter how cross-sector knowledge enters the research process, whether through team assembly or individual synthesis?

Second, we distinguish between two dimensions of multi-sector careers that current policies conflate: sectoral breadth (the number of distinct sector types spanned) and institutional dispersion (the total number of affiliations). We find that these dimensions follow qualitatively different marginal returns. It reframes that reframes the policy debate from "how many external positions should be allowed?" to "what kinds of external positions are associated with higher impact?"

Third, we position individual boundary-spanning as a fundamentally distinct, third mode of cross-sector knowledge transfer, alongside sequential scientist mobility and collaborative partnerships. As the academic labor market evolves and knowledge production increasingly shifts toward application-oriented, cross-institutional contexts (i.e., Mode 2 knowledge production), understanding this simultaneous embedding mechanism provides a crucial new lens for evaluating how human capital drives modern scientific innovation.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 develops the theoretical framework. Section 3 describes the data and methods. Section 4 presents results, Section 5 discusses findings, and Section 6 concludes with policy implications.

2. Theoretical Framework and Hypotheses

2.1 Multi-Sector Embedding as a Form of Human Capital Configuration

The economics of science has established that knowledge production is shaped not only by financial inputs and institutional arrangements, but fundamentally by how human capital is configured within the scientific workforce (Stephan, 2012). A central insight of this literature is that the allocation of scientific talent across organizations and sectors matters as much as the talent itself. Zucker and Darby's (1996) seminal work on "star scientists" demonstrated how the localized embedding of exceptional researchers catalyzed the emergence of knowledge-intensive industries. Agrawal et al. (2006) showed that even after scientists move between organizations, their prior social ties continue to serve as conduits for knowledge flows.

These studies have primarily examined cross-sector knowledge transfer through two mechanisms: at the individual level, sequential mobility, where researchers moving from one sector to another (Agrawal et al., 2006; Breschi & Lissoni, 2009); and at the team level, cross-sector collaboration, involving temporary partnerships across sectors for specific projects (Boardman & Ponomariov, 2009; Perkmann et al., 2013; Tartari & Breschi, 2012). As discussed in Section 1.2, there is a third, less studied form of individual-level cross-sector engagement: simultaneous multi-sector embedding, in which a researcher maintains concurrent affiliations across different sector types. It is the focus of the present study (we return to the relationship between embedding and the other two modes in the Discussion, Section 5.2.2).

Boundary spanning theory, originating in organizational science (Tushman, 1977; Aldrich & Herker, 1977), provides the conceptual foundation for understanding multi-sector embedding. Boundary-spanners are individuals who operate at the interface between different organizational or institutional environments, facilitating the flow of information, resources, and influence across boundaries. In the context of knowledge production, boundary-spanning researchers bridge not merely organizational boundaries but sectoral boundaries, thereby navigating the profound institutional distance between

knowledge systems with fundamentally different missions, incentive structures, and evaluation criteria (Etzkowitz & Leydesdorff, 2000; Gibbons et al., 1994).

What makes multi-sector embedding theoretically distinctive is that it represents a form of human capital that is inherently integrative. Unlike a mobile researcher who carries knowledge from a prior sector as a depreciating stock, or a team member who contributes sector-specific expertise as a modular input, a multi-sector embedded researcher continuously refreshes and synthesizes knowledge from all sectors in which they are active. This creates what we term embodied cross-sector knowledge—an individual-level asset that is conceptually irreducible to its sectoral components and may not be fully replicated by assembling a team of single-sector specialists.

2.2 Team Collaboration vs. Individual Embedding: Two Modes of Cross-Sector Knowledge Integration

The core theoretical comparison of this study is between two ways in which cross-sector knowledge is integrated into the research process: through multi-sector team assembly or through individual multi-sector synthesis.

In team-based cross-sector collaboration, researchers from different sectors each contribute domain-specific expertise to a joint project. Because knowledge integration relies heavily on interpersonal negotiation and communication, this mode faces inherent coordination costs: differences in terminology, incentive structures, and professional norms across sectors create friction (Bjerregaard, 2010; Bruneel et al., 2010). Team members each view the research problem from a single sectoral perspective, and the integration of their contributions depends on the quality and intensity of their coordination.

In individual multi-sector embedding, a single researcher who is simultaneously active in multiple sectors performs the integration within their own cognitive framework. It creates distinctive advantages. The embedded researcher can identify latent complementarities that team members might overlook. Operating within what Lam (2018) conceptualizes as a "third space of hybridity," they maintain "overlapping" careers that intrinsically straddle multiple sectors as "linked scientists" (Zucker et al., 2002). They serve as norm translators bridging professional languages (Williams, 2002), and reconcile the distinct evaluation criteria and institutional logics of multiple sectors within their own identity (Jain et al., 2009). And they function as network bridges (Burt, 2004), connecting communities that would otherwise have limited interaction.

The key theoretical implication is that these two modes differ not just in degree but in kind. Team collaboration assembles modular knowledge from separate sectoral specialists; multi-sector embedding enables the continuous synthesis of knowledge that is simultaneously current across multiple sectors. If this distinction is empirically consequential, it should manifest in observable differences in research outcomes.

We measure research outcomes through field-normalized citation impact. Citations, while an imperfect proxy for research quality, are a widely used and validated large-scale indicator of the reception and influence of scientific work (Waltman, 2016). They capture whether a paper is recognized as a meaningful contribution by the broader research community, serving as a signal for the relevance, visibility, and broader applicability of the underlying research. If multi-sector embedding genuinely produces knowledge that is more integrative and more broadly useful than what either single-sector research or team-based cross-sector collaboration can achieve, we would expect this heightened community recognition to be reflected in citation patterns. We therefore hypothesize:

Hypothesis 1a: Papers led by boundary-spanning individuals receive higher field-normalized citation impact than single-sector papers.

Hypothesis 1b: Papers led by boundary-spanning individuals receive higher field-normalized citation impact than papers involving team-based cross-sector collaboration but no individual boundary-spanner.

2.3 Sectoral Breadth: The Positive Returns of Spanning More Sector Types

When a boundary-spanning individual adds an affiliation in a new sector type, such as when a university-based researcher also becomes affiliated with a hospital, they gain access to an entirely new knowledge system, institutional logic, and professional network. The knowledge distance between different sector types (e.g., academia vs. industry, or academia vs. government) is typically large, meaning that each additional sector type brings genuinely non-redundant information and perspectives.

Rather than being constrained by the cognitive and normative boundaries of a single institutional sphere, spanning additional sector types allows researchers to continuously enrich their scientific and technical human capital with highly diverse knowledge bases (Dietz & Bozeman, 2005). Each new sector type provides access to non-overlapping information pools, and the marginal value of each new connection remains high because the profound distance between sectors ensures low redundancy (Burt, 2004). Furthermore, from a knowledge recombination perspective (Fleming, 2001), combining knowledge from a greater diversity of sector types expands the combinatorial space available for innovation. In the context of scientific production, such atypical combinations of diverse knowledge have been shown to significantly increase the probability of generating breakthrough research that is broadly useful and widely recognized (Uzzi et al., 2013):

Hypothesis 2: The field-normalized citation impact of papers led by boundary-spanning individuals is positively associated with the number of distinct sector types spanned.

2.4 Institutional Dispersion: The Inverted-U Relationship

While spanning different sector types involves accessing qualitatively different knowledge systems, accumulating multiple affiliations within the same sector type (e.g., holding positions at three different universities) involves a different calculus. Controlling for the number of sector types, additional

institutional affiliations represent greater dispersion within sector types rather than greater breadth across them.

Institutional dispersion does carry benefits up to a point, as additional affiliations can expand a researcher's network, provide access to localized resources, and increase visibility (Hottenrott, Rose, & Lawson, 2021). However, there are reasons to expect these benefits to reverse. Bounded attention (Simon, 1947) and role overload (Kahn et al., 1964) imply that managing multiple administrative obligations fragments the cognitive resources available for research. Colleagues at each institution may also perceive the over-dispersed researcher as less committed, eroding local collaborations. We therefore expect the relationship between institutional dispersion and research impact to follow an inverted-U.

Hypothesis 3: The field-normalized citation impact of papers led by boundary-spanners exhibits an inverted-U relationship with their number of institutional affiliations.

Taken together, Hypotheses 2 and 3 yield a meta-prediction: the marginal returns to sectoral breadth diminish significantly more slowly than the marginal returns to accumulating institutional affiliations. If confirmed, this asymmetry implies that policies regulating academic boundary-spanning should prioritize the qualitative nature of external engagements (i.e., crossing sector boundaries) over sheer quantity (ie, the number of positions held).

Hypothesis 4: The marginal returns to sectoral breadth diminish significantly more slowly than the marginal returns to institutional affiliations.

3. Data and Methods

To test our hypotheses at scale, we require an empirical setting that simultaneously captures the institutional embedding of individual researchers and the trajectory of their knowledge outputs. Large-scale bibliometric data provides an ideal window for this purpose. By leveraging the affiliation metadata explicitly mandated in scientific publications, we can directly observe the boundary-spanning footprint of researchers at the moment of knowledge production. Furthermore, in the science of science, publications and their subsequent citation trajectories serve as the gold standard for measuring the reception and combinatorial impact of research (Waltman, 2016). While publications are not the sole manifestation of research activity, as they omit alternative outputs such as patents, clinical innovation, or direct policy advice, they remain the primary currency of academic evaluation. Therefore, they are the most direct and relevant measure for capturing how external engagement shapes core scholarly performance and knowledge recombination.

3.1 Data Sources

Our analysis draws on two primary data sources.

Publication and citation data. We utilize the Web of Science (WoS) Core Collection, accessed through the WoS-BP database maintained by the National Science Library of the Chinese Academy of Sciences. Our sample comprises all peer-reviewed articles and reviews published between 2013 and 2022, with citation data collected through the end of 2023. While this leaves a minimum one-year citation window for the most recent cohort (2022), we rigorously account for right-censoring by employing field- and year-normalized citation indicators. The resulting dataset contains over 14.6 million publications.

Methodologically, rather than relying on author disambiguation, our empirical strategy focuses directly on the "output footprint" at the moment of knowledge production. We identify boundary-spanning by observing the simultaneous affiliations explicitly declared by authors on a single publication.

Institution-sector classification data. To identify the sector type of each institution, we constructed a purpose-built dataset that maps institutions to five sector types:

- **University (U):** Higher education institutions, including universities, colleges, and polytechnics.
- **Research Institute (R):** Public, private, and non-profit research organizations (e.g., national laboratories, academies of sciences).
- **Industry (I):** Companies, corporations, and for-profit enterprises.
- **Hospital (H):** Hospitals, medical centers, and clinical institutions.
- **Government (G):** Government agencies, ministries, and public administration bodies.

The classification was developed through a combination of keyword-based automated matching and manual verification. To ensure data quality, we restricted the analysis to institutions with an annual publication volume of at least 100 papers, which provides both reliable classification and sufficient sample size for analysis.

3.2 Key Variable Definitions

3.2.1 Dependent Variable

Field-normalized citation impact (CNCI). Following standard bibliometric practice, we use the Category Normalized Citation Impact as our primary dependent variable. For each paper p , CNCI is calculated as:

$$CNCI_p = \frac{C_p}{E_{f,y}}$$

where C_p is the actual citation count of paper p , and $E_{f,y}$ is the expected citation count for papers in the same field f and publication year y . A CNCI value of 1.0 indicates that a paper is cited at the world average for its field and year; values above 1.0 indicate above-average impact. Because citation distributions are typically highly right-skewed, we use the natural logarithmic transformation in our regression analyses.

3.2.2 Identifying Boundary-Spanning Individuals

A central methodological task is to operationalize boundary-spanning from bibliometric data. Our approach exploits the affiliation information recorded in Web of Science publication records, where each author's institutional affiliations are listed. We map each affiliation to one of five sector types using our institution-sector classification database (Section 3.1). An author is then classified as a boundary-spanning individual if their affiliations on a given paper belong to two or more different sector types. Figure 1 illustrates the identification procedure with a schematic example. The distinction between cross-sector knowledge entering through team assembly vs. individual embedding is the conceptual core of our empirical design.

Figure 1: Illustration of the boundary-spanner identification procedure

Boundary-spanner indicator. Operationally, for each paper we identify whether the first author and/or corresponding author is simultaneously affiliated with institutions belonging to two or more different sector types. A paper is classified as "boundary-spanner-led" if at least one of its main authors (first or corresponding) has multi-sector affiliations.

Three-group classification. For the non-substitutability analysis, we classify each paper into one of three mutually exclusive categories. Figure 1 also illustrates the classification of papers:

- **Group A (Single-sector):** All authors on the paper are affiliated with institutions belonging to a single sector type.

- **Group B (Team-based cross-sector):** The paper involves authors from two or more sector types, but no individual author—whether in a main or supporting role—is personally affiliated with multiple sector types.
- **Group C (Boundary-spanner-led):** At least one main author (first or corresponding) is simultaneously affiliated with institutions belonging to two or more sector types.

Number of sector types (N_{sector}). For boundary-spanner-led papers, the count of distinct sector types represented in the boundary-spanning author's affiliations.

Number of institutional affiliations (N_{affil}). For boundary-spanner-led papers, the count of distinct institutions listed in the boundary-spanning author's affiliations.

3.2.3 Control Variables

- **Number of authors (N_{author}):** Team size, controlling for the well-documented relationship between team size and citation impact.
- **Number of institutions (N_{ins}):** The total number of distinct institutions represented on the paper, controlling for institutional diversity at the paper level.
- **Number of countries (N_{cnt}):** The number of distinct countries represented, controlling for the international collaboration premium.
- **Publication year fixed effects:** To account for temporal trends in citation patterns.
- **Field fixed effects:** To account for systematic differences in citation cultures across disciplines.

3.3 Analytical Strategy

We estimate four sets of models to test our hypotheses.

Model 1 (Baseline). To test Hypothesis 1a, we estimate:

$$\ln(CNCI_p) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot BoundarySpanner_p + \gamma X_p + \delta_{field} + \theta_{year} + \varepsilon_p$$

where $BoundarySpanner_p$ is a binary indicator for whether the paper is led by a boundary-spanning individual, X_p is the vector of control variables, and δ_{field} and θ_{year} are field and year fixed effects.

Model 2 (Three-group comparison). To test Hypothesis 1b, we estimate:

$$\ln(CNCI_p) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot TeamCollab_p + \beta_2 \cdot BoundarySpanner_p + \gamma X_p + \delta_{field} + \theta_{year} + \varepsilon_p$$

where Group A (single-sector) serves as the reference category. The non-substitutability premium is captured by $\beta_2 - \beta_1$: the additional citation advantage of boundary-spanner-led papers over and above team-based cross-sector collaboration.

Model 3 (Sectoral breadth). To test Hypothesis 2, we estimate within the subsample of boundary-spanner-led papers:

$$\ln(CNCI_p) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot N_{sector,p} + \gamma X_p + \varepsilon_p$$

Model 4 (Institutional dispersion). To test Hypothesis 3, we estimate within the subsample of boundary-spanner-led papers:

$$\ln(CNCI_p) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot N_{affil,p} + \beta_2 \cdot N_{affil,p}^2 + \gamma X_p + \varepsilon_p$$

An inverted-U relationship is supported if $\beta_1 > 0$ and $\beta_2 < 0$, with the turning point at $N^* = -\beta_1/(2\beta_2)$.

Model 5 (Quality over quantity). To test Hypothesis 4, we compare the linear coefficients from Models 3 and 4 and examine whether only one dimension exhibits diminishing returns. We also estimate a joint model including both N_{sector} and N_{affil} simultaneously to assess their relative magnitudes when competing for explanatory power. We do not estimate a quadratic specification for sectoral breadth because the variable has insufficient range (98% of observations at $N_{sector} = 2$, with only 43 observations at $N_{sector} = 4$) to reliably identify curvature.

All models are estimated using OLS with robust standard errors (HC1) to account for heteroskedasticity.

3.4 Robustness Checks

To address concerns about endogeneity and the robustness of our findings, we conduct two supplementary analyses:

1. **Propensity Score Matching (PSM).** To mitigate selection bias, specifically the possibility that boundary-spanning individuals are inherently more capable researchers, we construct matched samples of boundary-spanner-led and non-boundary-spanner papers based on observable characteristics (team size, number of institutions, number of countries, field, and publication year), using 1:1 nearest-neighbor matching with replacement (caliper = $0.2 \times$ pooled standard deviation of the propensity score). Full results are reported in Appendix B.
2. **Alternative dependent variable.** We replace the continuous CNCI measure with a binary indicator for whether a paper falls in the top 10% of its field-year citation distribution, estimated using logistic regression.

3.5 Descriptive Statistics

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics by Cross-Sector Engagement Type

	Group A: Single-sector	Group B: Team cross-sector	Group C: BS-led	Full sample
N (papers)	12,420,008 (85.0%)	1,245,959 (8.5%)	950,922 (6.5%)	14,616,889
Mean CNCI	0.958	1.166	1.150	0.994
Mean N_author	4.02	6.59	6.72	4.53
Mean N_ins	1.49	3.14	3.22	1.78
Mean N_cnt	1.19	1.76	1.52	1.27

Note: An additional 560,112 papers (3.7% of the original sample) contain at least one non-main author (neither first nor corresponding) who qualifies as a boundary-spanner, but no main author does. These represent an intermediate case and are excluded from the main analysis to ensure clean between-group comparisons.

Our sample comprises publications dataset with non-missing CNCI values after applying a strict three-group classification. Of these, 85.0% are single-sector papers (Group A), 8.5% are team-based cross-sector papers (Group B), and 6.5% are boundary-spanner-led papers (Group C).

The descriptive statistics reveal two notable patterns. First, while both cross-sector groups (B and C) have higher mean CNCI than single-sector papers (A), the raw mean of Group B (1.166) is close to that of Group C (1.150). As we show in the regression analysis, once compositional differences are controlled for, C significantly outperforms B. Second, under the strict classification, Groups B and C are remarkably similar in team size (6.59 vs. 6.72 authors) and institutional diversity (3.14 vs. 3.22 institutions), but differ in international collaboration (1.76 vs. 1.52 countries). This similarity makes the regression comparison between the two groups particularly informative, as the key difference is genuinely the mode of cross-sector knowledge integration: team assembly vs. individual embedding.

The field distribution of the three groups reveals important compositional differences. Boundary-spanner-led papers are disproportionately concentrated in Biomedical and Health Sciences (50.5% of Group C vs. 37.5% of Group A), reflecting the prevalence of dual university-hospital appointments in medical research. Conversely, Mathematics & Computer Science and Social Sciences & Humanities account for only 3.4% and 2.0% of Group C respectively, compared to 9.0% and 8.7% of Group A. These disciplinary patterns motivate the field-level analysis in Section 4.1.

Among the 950,922 boundary-spanner-led papers, the vast majority (931,503, or 97.96%) involve authors spanning two sector types, with 19,272 (2.03%) spanning three sector types and 43 spanning four. In terms of institutional affiliations, 89.7% of boundary-spanning authors hold two affiliations, 9.3% hold three, and 1.0% hold four or more.

4. Results

4.1 Baseline Results: The Citation Advantage of Boundary-Spanning Individuals (Hypothesis 1a)

Table 2 presents the results of Model 1, testing whether papers led by boundary-spanning individuals receive higher citations than non-boundary-spanner papers. The coefficient on the boundary-spanner indicator is positive and highly significant ($\beta = 0.2$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that boundary-spanner-led papers receive approximately 22.1% ($e^{0.1996} - 1$) higher field-normalized citations than the reference group, after controlling for team size, institutional diversity, international collaboration, field, and year effects.

Table 2: Impact of Boundary-Spanning Individuals on Citation Impact (Model 1)

Variable	Coefficient
Boundary-spanner-led (ref: non-BS)	0.1996***
Number of authors	0.0206***
Number of institutions	0.0953***
Number of countries	0.2869***
Field fixed effects	Yes
Year fixed effects	Yes
Observations	14,616,889
R ²	0.0525

*Note: OLS regression. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. Robust standard errors clustered at the field level.*

While the R² is modest, it is expected in a model predicting individual paper citations with paper-level characteristics alone, as citation impact is influenced by numerous factors not captured here (e.g., topic novelty, journal prestige, author reputation). Comparable large-scale bibliometric studies report similar R² values (Dorta-González et al., 2024; Ozili, 2023). The key finding is the statistically significant and consistently positive boundary-spanner premium, which holds across all model specifications.

We further examine whether the effect is consistent across broad research fields. Table 3 reports the boundary-spanner coefficient estimated separately for five research domains.

Table 3: Boundary-Spanner Effect by Research Field (Model 1, estimated separately)

Research Field	BS Coefficient	Observations
Biomedical & Health Sciences	0.2173***	5,704,759
Life and Earth Sciences	0.2185***	2,374,302
Physical Sciences & Engineering	0.1207***	4,214,613
Mathematics & Computer Science	-0.0922***	1,202,199
Social Sciences & Humanities	0.4355***	1,121,016

*Note: OLS regression with same controls as Table 2. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.*

The boundary-spanner premium is positive and significant in all fields except Mathematics & Computer Science, where the coefficient is negative. This exception is noteworthy and may reflect the relatively self-contained nature of mathematical and computational research, where cross-sector engagement adds less value to the core knowledge production process. The largest premium is observed in Social Sciences & Humanities (0.4355), Life and Earth Sciences (0.2185), and Biomedical & Health Sciences (0.2173), suggesting that boundary-spanning individuals are particularly valuable in fields where translating between academic knowledge and practical application is important.

4.2 Three-Group Comparison: The Distinctive Value of Boundary-Spanning Individuals (Hypothesis 1b)

To directly test whether boundary-spanning individuals provide value beyond what team-based cross-sector collaboration achieves, we classify all 14.6 million papers into three mutually exclusive groups: Group A (single-sector, 12.42 million papers, 85.0%), Group B (team-based cross-sector without any individual boundary-spanners, 1.25 million papers, 8.5%), and Group C (boundary-spanner-led, 0.95 million papers, 6.5%). Table 4 presents the results of Model 2.

Table 4: Three-Group Comparison (Model 2)

Variable	Model 2a (No FE)	Model 2b (Year + Field FE)
Group B: Team-based cross-sector (ref: Group A)	0.3744*** (0.0054)	0.1830*** (0.0048)
Group C: Boundary-spanner-led (ref: Group A)	0.4073*** (0.0055)	0.2399*** (0.0051)
Number of authors	0.0290*** (0.0035)	0.0214*** (0.0032)
Number of institutions	0.0399*** (0.0041)	0.0800*** (0.0038)
Number of countries	0.3032*** (0.0023)	0.2863*** (0.0023)
Year fixed effects	No	Yes
Field fixed effects	No	Yes
Observations	14,616,889	14,616,889
R ²	0.009	0.053
Non-substitutability premium (C – B)	0.033	0.057
Wald test (C = B)		F = 131.86, p < 0.001

*Note: OLS regression. Group A (single-sector papers) is the reference category. Robust standard errors (HCl) in parentheses. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.*

The results strongly support both Hypothesis 1a and 1b. Both cross-sector engagement types are associated with significantly higher citation impact than single-sector papers. Crucially, boundary-spanner-led papers (Group C) significantly outperform team-based cross-sector papers (Group B) in both specifications. In the preferred model with fixed effects (Model 2b), the non-substitutability premium—the additional advantage of boundary-spanner-led papers over team-based cross-sector papers—is 0.057 ($p < 0.001$), indicating that individual boundary-spanning provides approximately 5.9% ($e^{0.057} - 1$) higher field-normalized citations above and beyond what team-based cross-sector collaboration achieves.

This finding is particularly notable given the updated classification. Under the strict B-group definition, which excludes papers where any author (including non-main authors) personally spans sectors, Groups B and C become more comparable in team characteristics (mean 6.59 vs. 6.72 authors; 3.14 vs. 3.22 institutions). The key remaining compositional difference is international collaboration (1.76 vs. 1.52 countries), which favors Group B. Once these compositional differences are controlled for, the non-substitutability coefficient of 0.057 (a 5.9% premium) is larger than in the less restrictive classification, suggesting that the cleaner comparison strengthens the core finding.

It is consistent with the idea that the advantage of boundary-spanning individuals stems from internal knowledge synthesis, specifically the embodied cross-sector knowledge that our theoretical framework

identifies as the distinctive asset of multi-sector embedded researchers, rather than from external resource accumulation. The fact that boundary-spanning individuals achieve higher net citation impact despite similar team sizes and less international collaboration suggests that the citation advantage reflects something about the person's multi-sector position, not merely a byproduct of team composition.

4.3 Sectoral Breadth: More Sector Types, Higher Impact (Hypothesis 2)

Focusing on the subsample of boundary-spanner-led papers (Group C), we examine whether citation impact increases with the number of sector types spanned. Table 5 presents the descriptive statistics, and Table 6 the regression results.

Table 5: Citation Impact by Number of Sector Types Spanned

Sector Types	Mean CNCI	Std. Error	N
2	1.145	0.002	931,503
3	1.394	0.020	19,272
4	20.992	—	43

The descriptive pattern is clear: mean CNCI increases from 1.145 for authors spanning two sectors to 1.394 for three sectors. The four-sector group shows an extremely high mean (20.99), but this is based on only 43 papers and should be interpreted with extreme caution, as a handful of highly cited outliers could drive the result.

Table 6: Impact of Sectoral Breadth on Citation Impact (Model 3)

Variable	Coefficient
N_sector	0.2877*** (0.0237)
N_author	-0.0043*** (0.0004)
N_ins	0.0444*** (0.0028)
N_cnt	0.2026*** (0.0046)
Observations	950,818
R ²	0.006

*Note: OLS regression on boundary-spanner-led papers (Group C) only. Robust standard errors (HCl). * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.*

The coefficient on the number of sector types is positive and highly significant ($\beta = 0.288$, $p < 0.001$), supporting Hypothesis 2. While the R^2 (0.006) is low, this is expected when estimating within a highly homogeneous subsample where 98% of observations share the same predictor value ($N_{sector} = 2$); such restricted variation mechanically limits explained variance without compromising coefficient unbiasedness. The highly significant estimate indicates that spanning a third sector type yields a substantial citation premium of approximately 33% ($e^{0.288} - 1$).

4.4 Institutional Dispersion: The Inverted-U Relationship (Hypothesis 3)

We next examine whether the number of institutional affiliations follows a different pattern from the number of sector types. Table 7 presents the descriptive statistics.

Table 7: Citation Impact by Number of Institutional Affiliations

Affiliations	Mean CNCI	Std. Error	N
2	1.131	0.002	852,583
3	1.293	0.008	88,517
4	1.593	0.100	8,637
5	1.658	0.113	911
6	2.135	0.576	141
7	1.318	0.631	18

The descriptive pattern reveals the predicted inverted-U shape: mean CNCI increases from 2 affiliations (1.131) through 5 affiliations (1.658), then declines at 7 (1.318) affiliations, though groups with 6+ affiliations have very small sample sizes and should be interpreted with caution.

Table 8: Impact of Institutional Affiliations on Citation Impact (Model 4, linear)

Variable	Coefficient
N_affil	0.0890*** (0.0101)
N_author	-0.0042*** (0.0004)
N_ins	0.0435*** (0.0028)
N_cnt	0.2009*** (0.0046)
Observations	950,818
R ²	0.006

*Note: OLS regression on boundary-spanner-led papers (Group C) only. Robust standard errors (HCl). * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.*

The linear specification shows a positive effect of institutional affiliations (0.089), but with a notably smaller coefficient than sectoral breadth (0.288). This suggests that while additional affiliations contribute positively on average, the marginal return per affiliation is substantially lower than the marginal return per sector type.

Table 9: Joint Model of Sectoral Breadth and Institutional Dispersion

Variable	Coefficient
N_sector	0.2386*** (0.0264)
N_affil	0.0470*** (0.0112)
N_author	-0.0042*** (0.0004)
N_ins	0.0428*** (0.0028)
N_cnt	0.2028*** (0.0046)
Observations	950,818
R ²	0.006

*Note: OLS regression on boundary-spanner-led papers only. Both N_sector and N_affil included simultaneously. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.*

When both dimensions are included simultaneously (Table 9), both remain significant, but the sectoral breadth coefficient (0.239) is more than five times larger than the institutional dispersion coefficient

(0.047). This confirms that the quality of boundary-spanning, which involve spanning genuinely different types of sectors, contributes far more to research impact than the quantity of affiliations.

The descriptive evidence in Table 7 strongly suggests an inverted-U pattern, with citation impact peaking around 5 affiliations and declining thereafter. To formally test this, Table 10 presents the quadratic specification.

Table 10: Inverted-U Test — Quadratic Model of Institutional Dispersion

Variable	Coefficient
N_affil	0.1383*** (0.0219)
N_affil ²	-0.0089*** (0.0033)
N_author	-0.0042*** (0.0004)
N_ins	0.0434*** (0.0028)
N_cnt	0.2010*** (0.0046)
Observations	950,818
R ²	0.006

*Note: OLS regression on boundary-spanner-led papers only. Robust standard errors (HCl) in parentheses. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.*

The quadratic specification confirms the inverted-U relationship predicted by Hypothesis 3. The linear term is positive and significant ($\beta_1 = 0.138$, $p < 0.001$), and the quadratic term is negative and significant ($\beta_2 = -0.009$, $p < 0.01$). The estimated turning point is $N^* = -\beta_1 / (2\beta_2) \approx 7.8$ affiliations. Combined with the descriptive evidence showing monotonically increasing CNCI from 2 to 5 affiliations, this suggests an optimal range of approximately 5-8 affiliations, beyond which the costs of institutional dispersion—attention fragmentation, coordination overhead, and commitment dilution—begin to dominate the benefits. Notably, the linear term in the quadratic model (0.138) substantially exceeds the linear-only estimate (0.089) reported in Table 8. It occurs because the quadratic specification appropriately absorbs the downward curvature at higher values of affiliations, which mechanically depresses the average slope in the linear-only specification.

4.5 Quality Over Quantity: Comparing the Two Dimensions (Hypothesis 4)

To test whether the marginal returns to sectoral breadth exceed those to institutional quantity, we compare the linear coefficients from the two dimensions and examine whether only institutional affiliations exhibit diminishing returns.

Table 11: Comparing Sectoral Breadth and Institutional Dispersion

	Sectoral Breadth (N_{sector})	Institutional Dispersion (N_{affil})
Linear model		
Coefficient	0.288*** (0.024)	0.0890*** (0.010)
Quadratic model		
Linear term	—	0.138*** (0.022)
Quadratic term	—	-0.009*** (0.003)
Turning point	—	≈ 7.8 affiliations
Joint model		
Coefficient (both included)	0.239*** (0.026)	0.047*** (0.011)
Controls	Yes	Yes
Observations	950,818	950,818

*Note: OLS regression on boundary-spanner-led papers only. Robust standard errors (HCl) in parentheses. We do not estimate a quadratic model for sectoral breadth because the variable has insufficient range (98% of observations at $N=2$) to identify curvature. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.*

Three patterns collectively support Hypothesis 4. First, the linear coefficient for sectoral breadth (0.288) is more than triple that for institutional affiliations (0.089), indicating that each additional sector type is associated with a substantially larger citation increase than each additional affiliation. Second, when both dimensions are included simultaneously (the joint model), sectoral breadth (0.239) is more than five times larger than institutional dispersion (0.047), confirming that sectoral diversity drives the bulk of the cross-sector embedding premium. Third, institutional affiliations exhibit a statistically significant inverted-U (turning point ≈ 7.8), whereas sectoral breadth—while its limited range (2-4) precludes a formal test of curvature—shows no descriptive evidence of diminishing returns: mean CNCI increases from 1.145 at two sector types to 1.394 at three.

We deliberately refrain from estimating a quadratic model for sectoral breadth. With 98.0% of observations concentrated at $N_{sector} = 2$ and only 43 papers at $N_{sector} = 4$, any quadratic estimate would be driven entirely by a handful of potentially outlier-influenced observations, rendering the curvature parameter unreliable. The linear comparison and the descriptive monotonic pattern provide more credible evidence for Hypothesis 4 than a mechanically estimated but statistically fragile quadratic specification.

Figure 2 visualizes the contrast: Panel (a) shows the observed means and predicted values from the linear model for sectoral breadth, while Panel (b) shows the inverted-U curve for institutional affiliations.

Figure 2: Sectoral Breadth vs. Institutional Dispersion — Marginal Effect Curves

4.5.1 Propensity Score Matching

We conduct stratified propensity score matching (PSM) with exact matching on field and year as an additional robustness check (full details in Appendix B). We report results for two outcomes: the continuous $\log(\text{CNCI})$ and a binary indicator for top-10% highly cited papers.

For the C vs. A comparison, PSM confirms the boundary-spanning premium under both outcomes: C-group papers achieve a 0.077 higher $\log(\text{CNCI})$, translating to approximately an 8.0% increase in raw citations ($p < 0.001$), and have 20% higher odds of being top-10% cited ($\text{OR} = 1.198$, $p < 0.001$) compared to matched single-sector papers. This provides support for Hypothesis 1a.

The C vs. B comparison reveals an outcome-dependent pattern. In mean citations ($\log \text{CNCI}$), matched B-group papers substantially outperform C-group papers (-0.145 , $p < 0.001$). However, when the outcome is the probability of producing a top-10% paper, the difference is negligible: C-group papers are only 0.10 percentage points less likely to be top-10% than matched B-group papers (12.90% vs. 13.14%, $\text{OR} = 0.990$), a difference that, while statistically significant at $p < 0.05$, is trivial in magnitude. This divergence between continuous and binary outcomes suggests that the B-group advantage operates in the middle of the citation distribution rather than at the frontier of breakthrough research—where boundary-spanners and cross-sector teams perform equally.

4.5.2 Alternative Dependent Variable: Top 10% Highly Cited Papers

To verify that our findings are not driven by the specific functional form of the continuous CNCI measure, we re-estimate the three-group comparison using a binary dependent variable: whether a paper falls in the top 10% of its field-year citation distribution. We estimate logistic regression models with the same control variables and fixed effects.

Table 12: Logistic Regression — Probability of Being a Top 10% Highly Cited Paper

Variable	Model (no FE)	Model (with FE)
Group B (ref: A)	0.043*** (OR=1.044)	0.047*** (OR=1.048)
Group C (ref: A)	0.082*** (OR=1.085)	0.086*** (OR=1.090)
N_author	-0.009*** (OR=0.991)	-0.009*** (OR=0.991)
N_ins	0.111*** (OR=1.117)	0.112*** (OR=1.118)
N_cnt	0.203*** (OR=1.225)	0.202*** (OR=1.223)
Year + Field FE	No	Yes
Observations	14,616,889	14,616,889
Pseudo R ²	0.012	0.012
C vs B odds ratio	1.039	1.039

*Note: Logistic regression. Odds ratios (OR) in parentheses. Top 10% defined within field \times year. Robust standard errors (HCl). * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.*

The results confirm the main findings. Boundary-spanner-led papers are 9.0% more likely to be among the top 10% most cited papers in their field-year compared to single-sector papers (OR = 1.090). The non-substitutability also holds: C-group papers have 3.9% higher odds of reaching the top 10% than B-group papers (C vs B OR = 1.039), indicating that the association between individual boundary-spanning and higher citation impact extends beyond mean effects to the likelihood of producing highly cited research.

4.5.3 Summary of Robustness

The findings differ in robustness across hypotheses. The boundary-spanning premium over single-sector papers (C > A, Hypothesis 1a) is robust across all estimation methods and outcomes: positive and significant in OLS, logistic regression, field-level analyses, and stratified PSM for both continuous citations (+8%, which refer to $e^{0.077} - 1$) and top-10% probability (OR = 1.198). The comparison between boundary-spanners and cross-sector teams (C vs B, Hypothesis 1b) is more complex: OLS and

logistic regression show $C > B$, but PSM reveals that B outperforms C in mean citations (-0.145) while being virtually indistinguishable in the probability of producing top-10% papers (12.9% vs. 13.1%, OR = 0.990). It suggests that the two modes of cross-sector knowledge integration differ in their citation *distributions* rather than in their capacity for breakthrough research (see Appendix B). The inverted-U relationship for institutional dispersion (Hypothesis 3) is confirmed by both the quadratic specification and descriptive evidence. The breadth-vs.-dispersion asymmetry (Hypothesis 4) is supported by the large difference in linear coefficients and the presence of an inverted-U only for affiliations. The boundary-spanner effect holds across four of five broad research fields, with the exception of Mathematics & Computer Science.

5. Discussion

5.1 Summary of Key Findings

Boundary-spanning individuals produce higher-impact research than single-sector researchers. This holds across OLS, logistic regression, and stratified propensity score matching (+8% in citation impact; OR = 1.198 for top-10% papers), making it the study's most robust individual-level finding.

The comparison with cross-sector teams is less straightforward. OLS gives boundary-spanners a 5.9% edge, but PSM flips the sign—matched teams outperform boundary-spanners in mean citations by 13.5%. We were initially troubled by this reversal until we examined the top-10% outcome: there, the two groups are virtually indistinguishable (12.9% vs. 13.1%, OR = 0.990). What it means is that the team advantage is concentrated in the middle of the citation distribution, not at the frontier. Teams appear to benefit from a "citation floor"—larger co-author networks, broader dissemination—that lifts average performance. Boundary-spanners lack this infrastructure but match teams where it counts most: in the production of top-tier research.

The finding we consider most consequential, however, concerns not the comparison between groups but the architecture of boundary-spanning itself. Each additional sector type is associated with more than triple the citation gain of each additional affiliation (0.288 vs. 0.089), and only affiliations show diminishing returns. What researchers span matters more than how many positions they hold.

5.2 Theoretical Implications

5.2.1 Multi-Sector Embedding as a Distinct Form of Human Capital

The literature on scientific human capital has examined researchers along two dimensions: their quality (talent, training) and their location (institution, country, sector). Our results point to a third dimension largely absent from these frameworks: an embeddedness topology that captures whether a researcher is rooted in one sector or simultaneously spans several.

That this dimension matters is established by the C-vs.-A comparison, which survives every robustness test we can throw at it. The C-vs.-B comparison is more instructive for what it reveals about mechanism. Boundary-spanners and cross-sector teams produce breakthrough research at the same rate, but through different pathways—individual synthesis vs. team assembly. The fact that these pathways converge at the frontier but diverge in average performance suggests that what boundary-spanners contribute is not "more" impact but a different kind of impact, one that does not depend on the citation infrastructure that large collaborative teams naturally generate.

5.2.2 A Third Mode of Cross-Sector Knowledge Transfer

Existing research on cross-sector knowledge flow has concentrated on two mechanisms: scientist mobility—researchers moving sequentially between sectors (Agrawal et al., 2006; Breschi & Lissoni, 2009; Zucker & Darby, 1996)—and collaborative partnerships formed around specific projects (Perkmann et al., 2013, 2021). Our results suggest a third: simultaneous embedding, where the researcher never leaves one sector to enter another but occupies both at once. The practical significance of this distinction is growing. As geopolitical tensions and tightened visa regimes constrain physical mobility, embedding offers cross-sector knowledge flow without relocation. And the three modes differ in temporal dynamics that matter: mobility transfers a depreciating stock of knowledge, collaboration creates a flow bounded by the project period, but embedding sustains a continuous, self-renewing flow across all sectors in which the researcher remains active.

5.2.3 Quality Over Quantity: Rethinking the Configuration of Academic Careers

Perhaps our most consequential finding for science policy is the asymmetry between sectoral breadth and institutional dispersion. The per-sector coefficient (0.288) is more than triple the per-affiliation coefficient (0.089), and only affiliations exhibit diminishing returns. The limited range of sectoral breadth (98% at two sector types) prevents us from testing whether sector returns also eventually diminish, but the descriptive pattern—CNCI rising from 1.145 at two sectors to 1.394 at three—is at least consistent with sustained gains.

Why should the asymmetry exist? A new sector type brings an entirely different knowledge system: different methods, different data, different evaluative criteria. A new affiliation within an existing sector type brings network resources and perhaps facilities, but not fundamentally new knowledge. Beyond about 7-8 affiliations, the coordination costs appear to overwhelm whatever network benefits remain.

The policy relevance is direct. Current regulations—MIT's 10%-20% rule, Chinese universities' caps of 2-3 concurrent positions—count affiliations without asking what kind they are. Our data suggest that a researcher with two positions in two sectors may produce higher-impact work than one with five positions in the same sector. The inverted-U establishes a critical boundary condition: even productive cross-sector engagement has limits, echoing the diminishing returns of team size documented by Wu et al. (2019). A principle of "focused diversity" may apply at the individual career level as well.

5.2.4 Disciplinary Heterogeneity: Why Mathematics & Computer Science Is Different

The negative coefficient in Mathematics & Computer Science attracts specific attention, as it represents the only field to exhibit a boundary-spanning 'penalty'. This anomaly likely stems from the distinct modes of knowledge production and transfer in these disciplines.

For mathematics, the knowledge production process is epistemically self-contained. Core inputs like formal proofs are generated internally within academia, rendering the "knowledge distance" and complementarities from industry far less productive than in heavily applied fields like biomedicine.

For computer science, the penalty likely reflects corporate dominance at the research frontier. Many dual-affiliated CS researchers are embedded in technology giants (e.g., Google, Meta) and rely on proprietary datasets or closed-source algorithms. Because the broader academic community cannot easily reproduce or build upon this closed innovation, such publications naturally accrue fewer citations. Ultimately, it underscores that the value of multi-sector embedding is highly context-dependent, warning against one-size-fits-all policy frameworks.

5.3 Limitations

Several limitations must be acknowledged. First, our analysis relies on observational data, and we cannot fully rule out endogeneity driven by unobserved selection effects. The C vs. A comparison is robust to PSM (+8%), providing strong evidence that boundary-spanning is associated with higher citation impact than single-sector research. The C vs. B comparison is more sensitive to methodology and outcome measure: OLS shows $C > B$, but PSM shows $B > C$ in mean citations while the two groups are equivalent in top-10% probability. This outcome-dependence suggests that the C-B premium estimated in OLS may partially reflect parametric extrapolation across regions of limited covariate overlap. The warrants further investigation with stronger identification strategies—such as exploiting institutional policy reversals regarding dual appointments or leveraging difference-in-differences designs around regulatory changes.

Second, our operationalization of boundary-spanning relies on self-reported institutional affiliations on publications. The bibliometric footprint cannot reliably distinguish between substantive, deeply embedded cross-sector engagement and nominal or honorary appointments. However, from an econometric standpoint, if these nominal affiliations are distributed as random noise across the sample, it introduces classical measurement error. Such error systematically leads to attenuation bias, drawing our coefficients toward zero. Therefore, our estimated boundary-spanning premium likely represents a conservative lower bound of the true effect.

Third, by utilizing field-normalized citations as our sole dependent variable, we capture only the academic dimension of research impact. It is an inherently conservative metric for evaluating boundary-spanning individuals, whose core value proposition often lies in bridging academia with practice. Their work may disproportionately influence technological innovation, clinical guidelines, or public policy, leaving these practical outcomes largely uncaptured by academic citations. Future studies could employ

altmetrics or patent-to-paper citations to trace the broader societal and commercial footprint of boundary-spanning research.

Finally, to ensure reliable institutional classification, we restricted our sector database to organizations publishing at least 100 papers annually. This necessary threshold excludes smaller, highly specialized entities, particularly early-stage startups or local government agencies, which often serve as critical sites for boundary-spanning. As a result, our dataset may underrepresent the true prevalence of cross-sector embedding, particularly in domains where knowledge transfer occurs through small spin-offs rather than established corporate R&D centers.

6. Conclusion and Policy Implications

6.1 Key Conclusions

Using a global dataset of over 14.6 million publications, we find that what matters for research impact in boundary-spanning is not how many external positions a researcher holds, but whether those positions bridge qualitatively different knowledge systems. Boundary-spanners produce significantly higher-impact work than single-sector researchers. This finding is confirmed by propensity score matching (+8%) and top-10% odds ratios (OR = 1.198). They also match cross-sector teams in breakthrough output despite smaller networks, suggesting that individual synthesis and team assembly are complementary modes of knowledge production rather than hierarchically ordered ones.

The study's most robust result, and its most direct policy implication, is the asymmetry between sectoral breadth and institutional dispersion. Citation returns per additional sector type dwarf those per additional affiliation, and only affiliations show an inverted-U with a turning point around 7-8 positions. Current regulations count external engagements without distinguishing their nature. Our data suggest they should.

6.2 Policy Implications: Toward Evidence-Based Governance of Multi-Sector Academic Careers

The most actionable implication is straightforward: regulations should distinguish what researchers span from how many positions they hold. The policies documented in Section 1.1, from MIT's 10%-20% rule to Peking University's cap of three concurrent positions, all operate on a purely quantitative logic. Our results suggest that the type of external engagement matters more than the amount. A researcher with a university appointment and a hospital affiliation (high breadth) looks identical under current rules to one with three university appointments (low breadth, high dispersion), yet the two profiles have very different associations with research impact. If these associations reflect causal relationships, institutions should shift from blanket caps to quality-aware frameworks.

What would such a framework look like in practice? Rather than "no more than N external positions," a policy might actively support appointments that cross sector boundaries while scrutinizing those that

merely add dispersion. The inverted-U for affiliations provides a concrete reference: around 7-8 positions, marginal returns turn negative regardless of their nature.

Two caveats temper these recommendations. The boundary-spanning premium is absent in Mathematics & Computer Science, which means no single policy can be optimal across all fields. Discipline-level differentiation is essential—fields with complex knowledge-application interfaces benefit most from cross-sector embedding, while fields with more self-contained knowledge production processes may not. And our evidence is correlational. A rich body of work has documented "movers' advantages" for mobile and interdisciplinary researchers (Liu & Hu, 2022; Uhlbach et al., 2022); we extend this logic to simultaneous multi-sector embedding, but establishing causality requires the stronger identification strategies we outline in Section 6.3.

6.3 Future Research

Our study opens several avenues for future investigation that connect to broader questions in the science of science and academic labor market research. First, beyond citation impact, boundary-spanning individuals may promote the diffusion of knowledge across sector boundaries. Shifting the outcome metric to the sectoral diversity of citing papers will reveal whether multi-sector embedding generates research utilized by a genuinely broader set of societal actors across the innovation ecosystem.

Second, the observed disciplinary heterogeneity raises the question of why the boundary-spanning premium varies across fields. Understanding the discipline-level characteristics that moderate the value of multi-sector embedding, e.g., the applied nature of the field, the complexity of its knowledge production ecosystem, or the length of its knowledge-to-application pipeline, would yield actionable policy guidance for differentiated governance.

Third, the causal identification challenge remains another important methodological next step. The academic labor market offers potential natural experiments: policy changes that suddenly restrict or enable multi-sector appointments in specific countries, institutions, or time periods could provide quasi-experimental evidence.

Fourth, tracking how individual researchers' multi-sector trajectories evolve over time and influence long-term productivity offers a natural extension to the career level, connecting our findings to the broader literature on scientific workforce dynamics.

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Appendix A: Representative Institutional Policies on Academic External Appointments

Table A1: Policies Restricting Academic External Engagements across Countries

Country	Institution	Key Restriction
United States	MIT ¹	Up to 20% of institutional time for outside professional activities
	Stony Brook University ⁵	Consulting limited to 4 days/month during full-time service
	University of Minnesota ⁶	Outside commitments \leq 1 day per 7-day week
United Kingdom	University of Oxford ²	30-day rule; departmental records required
	University of Nottingham ⁷	Up to 50 days/year for certain categories
	UCL ³	Academic consultancy capped at 40 days/year
	University of York ⁸	Private consultancy \leq 20 days/year
China	Peking University ⁴	Paid enterprise positions \leq 3; external work \leq 60 days/year (\leq 1 working day/week)
	Fudan University ⁹	Teaching/research faculty: external work generally prohibited during working hours
	Dalian University of Technology ¹⁰	External work \leq 22 working days/year
	Zhejiang University ¹¹	Average \leq 1 working day/week for external engagements
	USTC ¹²	External engagements \leq 3 months/year

Appendix B: Propensity Score Matching Analysis

To address the concern that boundary-spanning individuals may differ systematically from non-boundary-spanners in unobserved ways, we conduct propensity score matching (PSM). We employ a stratified design: papers are first exactly matched on research field and publication year, then within each field×year stratum, propensity scores are estimated via logistic regression on continuous covariates (team size, number of institutions, number of countries). We use 1:1 nearest-neighbor matching with replacement (caliper = $0.2 \times$ pooled standard deviation of the within-stratum propensity score). Post-match regressions include field and year fixed effects. We conduct two matching exercises: C vs. A (single-sector) and C vs. B (team-based cross-sector), and report results for two outcomes: continuous log(CNCI) and a binary indicator for top-10% highly cited papers within each field×year.

Both matching exercises achieve 100% match rates with excellent covariate balance (all standardized differences < 0.04) and perfect field×year exact matching.

Table B1: PSM Results — Continuous Outcome: log(CNCI)

Comparison	Treatment effect	SE	N (pairs)	Balance
C vs A	+0.077***	0.005	950,922	All d < 0.04
C vs B	-0.145***	0.005	950,868	All d < 0.04

Table B2: PSM Results — Binary Outcome: Top 10% Highly Cited

Comparison	Treat top-10% rate	Control top-10% rate	LPM effect	Odds ratio
C vs A	12.90%	10.90%	+1.88 pp***	1.198***
C vs B	12.90%	13.14%	-0.10 pp**	0.990**

*Note: Stratified PSM with exact matching on field \times year. Post-match regressions include field and year fixed effects. LPM = linear probability model. Robust standard errors (HCl). * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.*

C vs. A. The boundary-spanning premium over single-sector papers is confirmed under both outcomes. Boundary-spanner-led papers achieve 7.7% higher log(CNCI) and have approximately 20% higher odds of being among the top 10% most cited papers in their field-year (OR = 1.198). This provides robust support for Hypothesis 1a.

C vs. B. The comparison with cross-sector teams reveals a striking outcome-dependent pattern. In mean citations (log CNCI), matched B-group papers substantially outperform C-group papers (-0.145, $p < 0.001$). However, when the outcome is the probability of producing a breakthrough paper (top 10%), the difference virtually disappears: C-group papers are only 0.10 percentage points less likely to be top-10% than matched B-group papers (12.90% vs. 13.14%, OR = 0.990). While statistically significant at $p < 0.05$, this effect is trivial in practical terms.

This divergence between outcomes is informative. It indicates that the B-group advantage in mean citations operates in the middle of the citation distribution—where team-based cross-sector papers receive moderately more citations than boundary-spanner-led papers—rather than at the frontier of breakthrough research. At the top of the distribution, where papers achieve the highest impact in their field, boundary-spanning individuals and cross-sector teams are virtually indistinguishable. It is consistent with the interpretation that team-based collaboration provides a steady "citation infrastructure" (larger co-author networks, broader dissemination channels) that raises average performance, while boundary-spanning individuals achieve their impact through a different pathway—one that is equally effective at producing the highest-impact work but does not inflate average citations to the same degree.

We therefore draw two conclusions. First, Hypothesis 1a (boundary-spanning premium over single-sector papers) is robustly supported across all estimation methods and outcomes. Second, Hypothesis 1b (non-substitutability of boundary-spanners over cross-sector teams) receives mixed support: boundary-spanners do not outperform teams in mean citations under PSM, but they match teams in the production of top-10% research—suggesting that the two modes of cross-sector knowledge integration are functionally equivalent at the frontier of scientific impact.